
GLOBALIZATION AND HUMAN RIGHTS

Mohd Ashraf Ganaie Research Scholar at Madhya Pradesh Institute of Social Science Research, Ujjain
Shafiq Mohiuddin Research Scholar Department of Political Science Vikram University, Ujjain
ganaiemohdashraf@gmail.com :: Shafiqapolscince123@gmail.com

Abstract

Globalization is a multidimensional miracle; it involves a deepening and broadening of rapid trans-border exchanges due to developments in technology, communications, and media. There is enough evidence that the world wealth, in general, rapidly increasing due to the advance in science and technology and that it is more than enough to satisfy the needs of all the dwellers of the globe. What is needed is the globalization of human rights and prosperity and to improve the effects of globalization on human rights. Widespread violation of human rights leads to an increasing feelings of deprivation and injustice among the populations of the different countries of the world it was enhanced by the rapid and unprecedented advance in communication and information technologies, which really turned the world into a global village. The movement against the slave trade, and to fight the more indiscriminate or destructive forms of weaponry, are early examples of international movements to counter the negative side of international trade and technology. "Development of human rights acts as specified in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948 and the succeeding United Nations agreements was the result of globalization. The paper focuses on how globalization has affected human rights, for this the methodology used is historical and descriptive."

Keywords: Globalization, Human Rights, Universal Declaration, Populations.

INTRODUCTION

The strengthen recognition of human rights around the world as established by several international treaties and convention and speeches has with the on-going. Globalization becomes increasingly in danger (2002). Today scholars argue that the condition, which is the traditional bearer of human rights obligation, has lost control over the globalization process and those in fact other players such as financial institutions and international. Corporations are the ones shaping the growth. Clifford explains the complexity of globalization in regards to human rights by saying. On one hand, fresh technologies and new international norms may be a benefit for losses and activist, compulsory the world together and making it harder for tyrannical regime to act with impunity against its own people. On the other hand, the philosophy of free trade and the increase of international business corporations may break and pressure and demolish local control According to Donnelly states and international companies today want to break away from the expenses imposed by interest's state guarantee of economic and social goals. (1995) the resulting market pressure to confine national social welfare policies are more and more supplemented by pressures from global financial institutions. The state is view as the main bearer of obligation when it comes to defense globally protected human rights. In the present global financial system and other actors become important in regards to the safety or rather the violation of human rights (6-12 March 1995) these actors take in global financial institutions, global organizations and worldwide corporations. The present globalization and the policies adhering to it power a number of human rights both civil and political as well as economic, social and cultural rights. Globalization and the current economic system and policies can control and power state's household policy. As a result, economic combination, free trade, deregulation and privatization have been seen by many as a challenge to the international protection of human rights and mainly to the awareness of economic, social and cultural rights.

OBJECTIVES

1. To examine and study the present status of Globalization and Human Rights.
2. To explore the impact of globalization on human rights.

INTERNATIONAL RESPONSE

Surrounded by his report to the UN Millennium meeting (2011) Kofi Annan described the world of globalization as a new background for and a new connectivity among economic actors and activities throughout the globe. Globalization has been made potential by the progressive dismantling of barriers to do business and capital mobility, together with fundamental scientific advances and increasingly declining costs of transport, communication and computing. Its integrative reason seems inevitable, its thrust mouth-watering. While globalization is interpreted as internationalization, the term refers to a growth of contact and interdependence between countries. From this viewpoint, a more global world is one where more messages, ideas, goods, wealth, investments and people cross borders between national-state-territorial units. A second common logical dead-end in discussions of globalization has equated the idea with liberalization. In this container, globalization denotes a process of removing officially compulsory borders on movements of capital between countries in order to form an 'open' and 'borderless' world economy(1982). On this thoughtful, globalization occurs as powers that be reduce or put an end to regulatory measures like trade barriers, foreign-exchange boundaries, capital controls, and travel permit requirements. The growth of human rights law in reply to globalization is not new, and there is nothing inbuilt in the global organization that would stop further defensive measures. The resulting movement lead to the formation of the ILO in (1919). Not like all following global organizations, the ILO busies all the relevant actors in its operations from the opening. Using a tripartite structure of symbol, the ILO ensured the participation of business, employment, and governments in developing worker rights and relating shortage in developing countries to money owing or relating unemployment to privatization, or relating health decline to the control of medicine patents. "They also detail the aspects of deteriorations in human rights. in human rights, such as economic failure and lower standards of living, increasing discrimination, inequity, withdrawal of pleasure of basic requirements such as food, clean water, housing, and illiteracy.etc. The impact of the poor penalty of globalization on the pleasure of human rights is multidimensional; all aspects of human survival are they political, economic, social or cultural, are affected". Bhagwati J (2007).

HUMAN RIGHTS NGOS

Human Rights NGOs play a significant role both on the nationwide level as well as on the worldwide level and "over the past few decades a small army of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) advocating, monitoring and lobbying for human rights, led by bodies such as forgiveness global along with Human Rights wristwatch, have become grave participants in international relationships. Briyk (2002).Furthermore, today there are "thousands of working class NGOs in inferior quality countries, gathering information on particular issues and urgent their governments to live up to international human rights principles. As NGOs have increased in numbers they have come to play more important role in law government, and in the past two decades NGOs have shown their significance on the international sight by playing an important role in the work of human rights and the growth of international law. Human Rights NGOs rely on human rights theory for their authority, and they provide themselves the right to condemn governments based on Household law but also importantly global human rights treaties. NGOs also use global human rights treaties and norms to give good reason for and legitimize their work and events at home and out of the country. "Human Rights Watch and Global Justice these NGOs over and over again are a part of human rights networks but also have relations with working class NGOs that provide them with details and figures. Some have their own experts that visit entities and behavior does research that later get available at the NGOs and in media. Grassroots NGOs

like those existing in this report work in communities with a program that mostly includes sensible work with human rights. Their work and services can. Take in providing education not incomplete to human rights schooling sports, theatre, cinema, Music, art and dance, health care, accommodation, citizenship classes and services to people whose rights have been deserted or violated”(Kadragic, A.2006)

IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION ON HUMAN RIGHTS

There is collection of “human rights” in the form of economic rights, labour rights, cultural rights, social and political rights etc. The globalization is careful to have an impact on the following rights such as (2013) Pp18-24.

- The rights of entry to the WTO of nations that violate human rights extinguish opportunities for costly sanctions to depress such violations.
- Unlock trade causes creation to move to areas everywhere ecological standards are negligent and outcome in environmental poverty. Similarly, the ready for action pressure that result from open deal cause regulator to lose control over local narrow matters and sudden a race to the bottom over matters such as social benefit standards, environmental principles, and worker defense legislation.
- Open trade exacerbate inequality in the distribution of income
- Liberty from brutal, cruel or degrading treatment,
- Liberty from servitude, the right to equal opportunity and non-discrimination
- The correct to an enough normal of living (including the right to sufficient food, clothing and housing), The right to maintain a high standard of physical and mental health,
- The right to work accompany by the right to just and fair-haired conditions of labour,
- Freedom of association and assembly and the right to collective bargaining have been severely impaired.

Just beginning States are, more over and over again than not, required by the dynamics of globalization to take measures that negatively impact on the enjoyment of those rights (Oloka-Onyango & Udagama, 1999). “Globalization has not caused “developing” countries to catch up with the developed world. Inequality has risen during this present globalization period. The developed world their intellectuals and policy makers –view globalization as “providing good opportunities for their countries and their people” Arafat, S. (2013) p16.

POVERTY AND INEQUALITY

If the problems of inequality in Brazil would be resolved I think Brazil Would be one of the best seats to live in the world (2006). Brazil has been classified as “a middle income country with a high incidence of Poverty and inequality and belongs to both the developed and the upward world where modernity and backwardness live side by side. According to recent figures from the UNDP, the GDP per capita is \$7,790, which puts it in the middle of the center profits countries in the globe. “On the other hand, this number does not signify the reality in Brazil or Rio de Janeiro very well since one of the most outstanding skins of Brazilian society is disparity. Brazil together with Sierra Leone has the second most unequal distribution of income in the world. Brazil has for a long time been in the top five most unequal countries in the world and is by far the most unequal country in South America. People continue to go hungry, continue to suffer from deficiency, and continue to walk kilometers to get water that is dirty, that is foul, and that will kill half of the people of the village because they don’t have situation of basic sanitation Thus, poverty and human Rights violations in Brazil go hand in hand and “total communities of the poor are being mistreated and the poor have become scapegoats of the evils resulting from long-term social leaving behind it is clear that the main factors at the back most of the human rights violations

are problems of inequalities, lack of public services and equal opportunities as well as poverty” Nault, M.D. & England, S. L. (Ed.2011).

SUGGESTIONS

A global watch should be recognized to keep an eye on and report the immoral transactions that take place stuck between the governments of developing nations and global corporations. The governments of developing nations should not carry on getting wealthy by selling their factors of manufacture land labour to global corporations” Report of the Human Rights Committee (1982)

- Supplies to become a free trading nation should be revised. Present requirements eliminate many upward countries. Urbanized countries need to perform more to support by creation it easier for rising countries to profit from trade and savings.
- Treaty-based device focusing on the household tasks of multilaterals as well as private actors in defensive human rights is a very significant step in the current financial atmosphere.
- Labors by states to create investments rules must be subjected to inspection and analyzed through human rights dialogue.

CONCLUSION

During a period of globalization, “the fight for human rights has become more compound and demanding. Realizing human rights particularly financially viable and community rights are fetching increasingly easier said than done. One of the most philosophical challenges that we face as a neighborhood of nations is to know better the rising socio-economic forces and forms of globalization, to form them to serve our needs and to respond successfully to their harmful penalty. Human rights can equilibrium forces of globalization within a just global legal framework. Maintaining balance between globalization and defense of human rights has to be a right of way” Human rights are what make us human being. They are the main beliefs by which we create the sacred home for human distinction. Human rights are what reason requires and sense of right and wrong orders.

REFERENCES

1. Arafat, S. (2013). Globalization and human rights: An overview of its impact. American Journal of humanities and social sciences, 1(1), 18-24
2. Bhagwati, J. (2007) in defense of globalization. London: Oxford University Press.
3. Brysk, A. (Ed.) (2002).Globalization and Human Rights. Berkeley: University of California Press.
4. Kadragic, A. (2006) Globalization and Human Rights. Philadelphia: Chelsea House Company.
5. Kadraglc, A. (2006).Globalization and Human Rights. Philadelphia: Chelsea House Publishers.
6. Nault, M.D. & England, S. L. (Ed.). (2011).Globalization and human rights in the Developing world. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
7. Report of the Human Rights Committee (1982). Official records of the general assembly, Thirty-seventh Session, Supplement No. 40, (A/37/40), annex V.
8. Report of the World Summit for Social Development (1995). Copenhagen, 6-12 March 1995, United Nations publication, Sales No. E.96 .IV.8), chap.
9. Robinson, M. (2002).UN high commissioner for human rights ethics. Human rights and globalization second global ethic lecture. The Global Ethic Foundation University of Tubingen, Germany.
10. Stephens, B. (2002). The amorality of profit: transnational corporations and human rights’. Berkeley Journal of International Law, pp. 20-45.
11. U.N. (2000). Globalization and its impact on the full enjoyment of all human rights: Preliminary report of the secretary-General, U.N. GAOR, 55th Sess., 5
12. UN (2005). Globalization and its impact on the full enjoyment of all human rights.’ UNGA,